

The Influence of Green Human Resource Management on Pro-Environmental Performance with Environmental Awareness as Mediation and Leadership Serving as Moderators

Nurfitri Kurniawati¹, Asri Laksmi Riani²

¹Master of Management/ Uninvestias Sebelas March, Indonesia

²Faculty of Economics and Business/ Uninvestias Sebelas March, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Nearly a century and a half of global industrial development has created significant environmental problems in many countries. This requires public attention to environmental or Green issues, including energy conservation, recycling, and renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and geothermal energy. Among these industries, the hospitality industry has made a positive impact on environmental conservation through reduced energy and water consumption, better use of durable and consumable items, and reduction in the generation of solid and hazardous waste. Therefore, the current research focuses on exploring the mediating role of one affective determinant, i.e., affective affinity for nature, and one cognitive determinant, i.e., awareness of risk to nature. These two factors have been identified as significant independent determinants of pro-environmental commitments. The study used cross-sectional surveys to collect data. The research was carried out through the distribution of questionnaires with a choice of Likert scale answers. The research population is hotel employees in Surakarta with a sample of 120 respondents. Green Human Resource Management has no effect on Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance. Green Human Resource Management has no effect on the Proactive Related Environmental Pro Performance. Green Human Resource Management has no effect on Environmental Commitment. Environmental Awareness fully mediates the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance. Environmental Awareness fully mediates the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Proactive Environmental Pro-Performance. Environmental Awareness fully mediates the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Environmental Commitment. Serving Leadership does not moderate the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance.

KEYWORDS: Environmental Awareness, Green Human Resource Management, Leadership Serving, Pro-Environmental Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Nearly a century and a half of global industrial development has created significant environmental problems in many countries (Watson & Tidd, 2018). For example, activities carried out in the tourism industry cause environmental problems such as climate change; loss of natural resources; emissions of various environmental pollutants that impact air and water, as well as emissions of noise and light pollution; and even species extinctions. These industrial processes and their destructive effects threaten the global environment, as well as economic and social well-being.

This requires public attention to environmental or Green issues, including energy conservation, recycling, and renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and geothermal energy (Ecer, Pamucar, Mardani, & Alrasheedi, 2021). In particular, the dangers of environmental issues have caused some industries to show a tendency to focus on Green performance and start educating and training their employees in Green performance in recent years. Among these industries, the hospitality industry has had a positive impact on environmental conservation through reduced energy and water consumption, better use of durable and consumable items, and reduction in the generation of solid and hazardous waste (Gürlek & Tuna, 2018; Kim, Lee, & Fairhurst, 2017; Pham, Tučkova, & Jabbour, 2019).

Tourism and hospitality researchers have studied a wide range of Green topics, including Green management, Green Human Resource Management, Green policies and practices, Green innovation, Green work attitudes, and green outcomes (e.g., Cabral & Jabbour,

2020; Gürlek & Koseoglu, 2021; Jaaron & Back-home, 2019; Mzembe, Melissen, & Novakovic, 2019; Peng, Lee, & Lu, 2020). Among these studies, the role of Green Human Resource Management practices in environmental outcomes is particularly prominent, with some researchers focusing on this area (e.g., Pham, Hoang, & Phan, 2019; Yong, Yusliza, & Fawehinmi, 2019; Zhang, Luo, Zhang, & Zhao, 2019). Green Human Resource Management is one of the most important aspects of an environmental human resource system. Green Human Resource Management is based on an eco-friendly perspective and aims to promote a Green organizational culture to encourage employees to do their jobs in the most environmentally friendly way. In addition, Green management focuses on educating the workforce about environmental goals and creating a competitive advantage based on environmental considerations. Referring to the existing Green Human Resource Management policies and principles, such management entails fostering a commitment among employees to the environment and teamwork in this area, and to recruit, reward, encourage personal growth, and train employees in line with the organization's environmental goals. (Kim et al., 2017; Pham, Hoang, & Phan, 2019).

However, although the relationship between Green Human Resource Management practices and Pro-Environmental Performance is well established, Chaudhary (2020) claims that any study of how Green Human Resource Management will shape Green performance, is incomplete without considering the process. Indeed, recent research has highlighted the lack of research on the processes by which Green Human Resource Management leads to pro-environmental behavior (Pham, Thanh, Tučkova, & Thuy, 2020). Pham, Tučkova, and Jabbour (2019) emphasized the lack of in-depth studies on the relationship between Green Human Resource Management practices and existing factors, such as Green employee performance, Green human capital, intermediary roles, and interactions between Green Human Resource Management practices. in organizational performance. Chaudhary (2020) proposes that alternative mediation mechanisms should be examined to better understand the dynamics of the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Pro-Environmental Performance. To address this gap, this study examines the process of the mediating role of environmental awareness in the causal relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Pro-Environmental Performance related to tasks and proactiveness.

In addition, as highlighted by Pham, Hoang, and Phan (2019), there is a need for further research on the role of interaction between Green Human Resource Management practices and organizational Green outcomes, as well as on how Human Resource Management affects employee awareness, knowledge and motivation to engage in Green activities within organizations. The literature shows that leadership contributes to optimal organizational outcomes by influencing organizational attitudes and performance (Khuwaja, Ahmed, Abid, Adeel, & Wanasika, 2020; Saleem, Zhang, Gopinath, & Adeel, 2020). In particular, stewardship leadership has been identified as one of the influential factors that moderate the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and the performance of Green organizations (Ying, Faraz, Ahmed, & Raza, 2020). A feature of servant leadership traits is that they are willing to sacrifice and are more likely to instill a sense of community interest among employees. Servant leadership pays considerable attention to community service (Ying et al., 2020), while Green Human Resource Management and Pro-Environmental Performance are closely aligned with protecting the environment and society by considering and minimizing environmental concerns. Therefore, it is important to examine how ministering leadership moderates these relationships (Ying et al., 2020).

There are four important aspects of affective affinity for nature: love of nature, feeling free in nature, feeling safe in nature, and feeling of oneness with nature (Kals, Schumacher, & Montada, 1999). Some theorists propose that affective affinity is essential in promoting stronger pro-environmental tendencies (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993), which is supported by empirical evidence (e.g., Mayer & Frantz, 2004). In particular, Müller et al. (2009) found that stronger affective affinity for nature predicted stronger pro-environmental commitment.

To advance an understanding of how Green Human Resources and Environmental Awareness, which are common factors, can influence people's pro-environmental commitments, we examine the underlying mechanisms by exploring the potential mediating roles of the two. Ten stronger pro-environmental tendencies were found, developed through changes in people's cognitive reasoning, for environmental issues or through the reinforcement of people's affective experiences with nature (e.g., Collado, Staats, & Corraliza, 2013; Hinds & Sparks, 2008). The current research focuses on exploring the mediating role of one affective determinant, i.e., affective affinity for nature, and one cognitive determinant, i.e., awareness of risk to nature. These two factors have been identified as significant determinants independent of pro-environmental commitments (Müller et al., 2009).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management is a strategic approach to effectively managing employees in an organization so that they help their business gain a competitive advantage. It is structured and designed to maximize employee performance in meeting the employer's strategic objectives. Green Human Resource Management can be defined as Human Resource Management practices and policies that sustain the business and, more importantly, aim to prevent damage arising from anti-environmental activities within the organization (Yusoff, Nejati, Kee, & Amran, 2020).

Environmental Pro Performance

Pro-environmental behavior, which is a behavior that consciously seeks to minimize the negative impact of individual actions on nature and the built world, can be an effective way to achieve an effective workplace sustainability program (Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002). It refers to employee activities that aim to reduce the negative consequences of community actions, such as by recycling, reducing waste, conserving water, and reducing energy consumption (Stern, 2000). Task-related Pro-Environmental Performance and Pro-Environmental Pro-Performance are grouped under the category of pro-environmental behavior (Bissing-Olson, Iyer, Fielding, & Zacher, 2013; Zhang et al., 2019). Task-Related Environmental Pro Performance refers to behaviors that are formally required by the organization and defined in the context of employee duties (Norton, Zacher, & Ashkanasy, 2014). Task-Related Environmental Pro Performance is the performance of employees from their important tasks in an environmentally friendly manner. Therefore, special attention is paid to the number of employees who perform their primary organizational duties in a way that helps protect natural resources and the environment (Bissing-Olson et al., 2013). The concept of Proactive Environmental Pro Performance refers to the level of employee initiative in Green behavior that goes beyond the employee's job responsibilities. This type of behavior does not originate from job conditions or job descriptions but arises from personal involvement in working with unexpected problems (Bissing-Olson et al., 2013). Proactive Environmental Pro Performance, which is a relatively understudied area (Ahmed et al., 2021; Tian, Zhang, & Li, 2020), is a key construct in this research because it involves a dependent and proactive approach to work, such as by providing environmental recommendations, making necessary changes, identifying environmental problems, and finding solutions to those problems.

Green Resource Management and Pro-Environmental Performance

Green behavior of employees can be promoted by organizations to minimize negative impacts and maximize positive impacts on the environment (Norton, Zacher, Parker, & Ashkanasy, 2017). Employees can be eco-friendly while performing their assigned tasks. In addition, they can make broader and "greener" changes to their workplace policies that are supported by the organization (Ramus & Steger, 2000).

Environmental Awareness

Environmental awareness is a multidimensional concept that is known to influence individual information, knowledge, attitudes, tendencies, behaviors, intentions, efforts, and actions (Wan, Chan, & Huang, 2017). This is related to the psychological factors that determine people's tendency towards pro-environmental activities, attitudes, and behaviors (Zhang, Zhang, Zhang, & Cheng, 2014). An environmental or pro-environmental person is someone who is involved in various P-EBs and activities and has certain values and attitudes (Yeh, Ma, & Huan, 2016). Higher awareness of the environment and related issues leads to a better understanding of the importance of environmental protection for human well-being. Environmental awareness concentrates on the "4 R's": reduce, reuse, recycle, and rethink (Gabarda- Mallorquí, Fraguell, & Ribas, 2018). This refers to the understanding that the environment is fragile and it is important to take care of the environment. Promoting environmental awareness requires a deep understanding of environmental issues, which is an effective way to improve environmental behavior and Green performance. Environmental awareness is a key construct in this study because the core nature of sustainability and environmental awareness addresses the issue of Human Resource Management as a strategic tool both to raise awareness and to green organizations and society at large (Benevene & Buonomo, 2020).

Environmental Commitment

Considering environmental issues at a strategic level benefits organizations because it allows organizations to recognize new business prospects using environmental performance as a source of strategic advantage (Bansal & Roth, 2000). The researchers further assert

that top management teams understand a commitment to environmental issues leads to a competitive advantage through lower costs, higher market sharing, improved image, and technological leadership. Harian et al. (2007) affirmed that the top management team can function as a steward of change to help organizations implement environmental management systems. Top management commitment is necessary for companies that will like to be considered environmentally friendly because this commitment contributes to improved environmental performance (Colwell & Joshi, 2013). An environmentally-conscious top management team can effectively coordinate environmental management activities across departments, as well as company boundaries (Teixeira et al., 2016). They further assert that a top management team with a concern for environmental issues is considered an intangible asset in the context of sustainable environmental improvement. When senior management recognizes the possible benefits of environmental initiatives, they will commit to participating in measures that will ultimately improve environmental performance (Latan et al., 2018). Spencer et al. (2013) found that companies that follow more sophisticated structures to achieve their environmental performance goals reflect management's top commitment to environmental sustainability. The participation of top management in managing the sustainability of an organization is one of the main drivers of the success of sustainable development in an organization. Top managers not only provide employees with resources and act as model roles to facilitate sustainability initiatives, they also build an organization's green culture through their active commitment and leadership (Kiesnere & Baumgartner, 2019). In contrast, research has shown that a lack of top management's commitment to the environment will lead to environmental efforts failing, leading to poor environmental performance.

Servant Leadership

Servant leadership focuses on serving individuals rather than individuals working to serve leaders, and a servant leader is someone who aims to serve others and ensure that the needs of others are met (van Dierendonck, 2011). According to the philosophy of servant leadership, a servant leader describes an altruistic personality that supports followers and helps them grow and learn by providing opportunities to experience and improve their material and spiritual conditions (Eva, Robin, Sendjaya, van Dierendonck, & Liden, 2019). One of the important characteristics of a servant leader that distinguishes him from other types of leaders is that he cares and cares about the community. Given their holistic view of the organization, environment, and society, service leaders are active in providing support, direction, and resources to followers. Service stylists are one of the key features of a serving leader, according to whom the leader presents themselves as role models for social responsibility performance. In the area of Green performance, serving leaders improve their followers' positive understanding of pro-environmental behavior by modeling the role of environmental values (Ying et al., 2020). A serving leader assumes his or her moral responsibility to protect the interests of all stakeholders, including staff and clients, to create value for the community, and to be mindful of community service. Leaders who serve act selflessly and seek to expand their subordinates' sense of concern for the community (Eva et al., 2019). Servant leadership is one of the key constructions of this study because of its peculiarity and ability to explain different outcomes better than other forms of leadership (Hoch, Bommer, Dulebohn, & Wu, 2018; Ying et al., 2020).

METHODS

The study used cross-sectional surveys to collect data. The research was conducted in the city of Surakarta, Indonesia. Number of samples 120 hotel employees in Surakarta, Indonesia. Data analysis using Smart PLS 3.0.

RESULT

Outer Model

A questionnaire is declared valid if the research instrument is really able to measure what should be measured (Wahyudi, Khoiriyah & Haryanto, 2015). The validity test in this study was carried out using the loading factor and Average Variance Extraction techniques using the help of Smart PLS 3.0 software.

Figure 1. Loading Factor

As a general rule, loading above 0.71 is very good, 0.63 is very good, 0.55 is good, 0.45 is fair, and 0.32 is poor (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). In Figure 1 above, it shows that the loading factor gives a value above the value of 0.7 which can be categorized as very good. So that the indicators used in this study are valid or have met convergent validity.

Table 1. Convergent Validity and Reliability Test

Variable	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reability
Green Human Resources (GHRM)	0.785	0.909	0.936
Environmental Awareness (KL)	0.751	0.933	0.948
Serving Leadership (KM)	0.553	0.838	0.878
Environmental Commitment (KOL)	0.836	0.935	0.953
Performance Pro Milieu Related to Tasks (KPLTR)	0.859	0.945	0.960
Proactive Environmental Pro Performance (KPLP)	0.874	0.928	0.954

The average variance extracted (AVE) value should be > 0.5 (Ghozali and Latan, 2015) or the model has sufficient differentiation if the AVE root for each construct is greater than the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model and early stage research in the development of the measurement scale, the loading factor value of 0.5-0.6 is still considered sufficient (Chin et al, 1997 in Ghozali and Latan, 2015). In Table 2, AVE gives a value of 0.5 for all indicators used in the study so that the indicators used in this study are valid or have met *convergent validity*. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reability scores are above 0.7 which can be categorized as very good. So that the indicators used in this study have Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reability values which can be categorized as having high reliability values.

Inner Model

The next step after the evaluation of the measurement model is the evaluation of the structural model to test the hypothesis proposed earlier. This analysis is carried out by testing the direct and indirect influence between the hypothesized variables. The following are the results of the PLS-SEM analysis:

Table 2. R-Square

Variable	R-Square
Environmental Awareness (KL)	0.750
Environmental Commitment (KOL)	0.705
Performance Pro Milieu Related to Tasks (KPLTR)	0.738
Proactive Environmental Pro Performance (KPLP)	0.743

The Human Resource Management variable can affect the Environmental Awareness variable by 0.750 and the remaining 0.250 is influenced by other variables. The Human Resource Management variable can affect the Environmental Commitment variable by 0.705 and the remaining 0.295 is influenced by other variables. The Human Resources variable can affect the Task-Related Pro Environmental Performance variable by 0.738 and the remaining 0.262 is affected by other variables. The Human Resources variable can affect the Proactive Environmental Pro Performance variable by 0.743 and the remaining 0.257 is influenced by other variables.

Table 3. Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Hypothesis 1a	GHRM -> KLPTR	0.282	0.286	0.159	1.772	0.077
Hypothesis 1b	GHRM-> KPLP	0.226	0.221	0.138	1.638	0.102
Hypothesis 1c	GHRM-> CABBAGE	0.255	0.249	0.166	1.533	0.126
Hypothesis 2a	GHRM -> KL -> KLPTR	0.291	0.304	0.123	2.367	0.018
Hypothesis 2b	GHRM-> KL -> KPLP	0.226	0.232	0.103	2.194	0.029
Hypothesis 2c	GHRM -> KL -> CABBAGE	0.250	0.248	0.120	2.073	0.039
Hypothesis 3a	GHRM * KM 1 -> KPLTR	-0.070	-0,062	0.052	1.336	0.182
Hypothesis 3b	GHRM * KM 2 -> KPLP	-0.111	-0.107	0.051	2.161	0.031
Hypothesis 3c	GHRM * KM 3 -> CABBAGE	-0.058	-0.055	0.050	1.149	0.251

DISCUSSION

The results of the H1a test show that Green Human Resource Management has no effect on the performance of pro-environment related tasks. This is contrary to Mahlaga et al. (2022) who said that there is a direct and significant relationship between Green

Human Resource Management and Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance. That is to show that if employees are aware of the benefits of using Green practices and their consequences, they are likely to be environmentally friendly within the organization and, more importantly, they will voluntarily engage with the company's Green activities. Green Human Resource Management practices will positively influence the behavior of environmentally friendly employees and improve the organization's environmental productivity programs. Pham et al. (2019) also argue that environmental productivity programs and practices enable the creation of environmentally sensitive, resource-efficient, and socially responsible organizations and lead employees to adopt a Green orientation in the organization (Pham, Tučkova, & Jabbour, 2019). Employees' good understanding of Green Human Resource Management practices leads them to interact better with Task-Related Environmental Pro Performance (Tian et al., 2020).

The results of the H1b test show that Green Human Resource Management has no effect on the performance of proactive environmental pros. This is contrary to Mahlaga et al. (2022) who said that Green Human Resource Management is directly and significantly related to Proactive Environmental Pro Performance and extra-role environmental behavior in the workplace (Chaudhary, 2020; Dumont et al., 2017; Saeed et al., 2019). It can be said that Proactive Environmental Pro Performance is characterized as an employee's initiative to take part in Green behavior in addition to their regular job duties. Employees under Green Human Resource Management play a crucial role in helping organizations proactively adopt environmental sustainability, and that employees improve the organization's environmental performance with their Proactive Environmental Pro Performance (Ahmed et al., 2021). Green Human Resource Management policies and practices focus on facilitating and sharing information with employees to develop their Green capabilities, to encourage them to engage in Green activities, and to create Green opportunities for employees' proactive environmental performance (Aragon-Correa, Martin-Tapia, & Hurtado-Torres, 2013; Shafaei, Nejati, & Mohd, 2020).

The results of the H1c test show that h1c is rejected and h0 is accepted, so it can be concluded that Green Human Resource Management has no effect on Environmental Performance. In line with Zhang's thinking, there doesn't seem to be enough practical research done to link Green Human Resource Management with employees' Pro-Environmental Performance through environmental awareness (Zhang et al., 2019). Thus, the existence of further studies should be carried out to understand the underlying mechanisms of Green Human Resource Management and Pro-Environmental Performance related to tasks and proactiveness, such as environmental awareness.

The results of the H2a test show that Environmental Awareness mediates the influence of Human Resource Management on Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance, with the results showing that h2a is accepted and h0 is rejected, then it can be concluded that Environmental Awareness fully mediates the influence of Human Resource Management on Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance. This is in line with what is suggested (Zhang et al., 2019). In order to implement Green Human Resource Management in the organization leads to the environmental awareness of the employees and then directly to the Pro-Environmental Performance related to tasks and is proactive in the organization.

The results of the H2b test confirm a significant indirect relationship between green Human Resource Management and proactive environmental performance of employees through the mediation role of Environmental Awareness. These findings, in line with Kim et al. (2019) and Roscoe et al. (2019), suggest that if employees have a better understanding of the environment and know that they can make a significant contribution to its protection, then they are responsible for engaging with environmental issues and activities. It can also be said that environmental awareness is the result of greening.

The results of the H2c test also confirm a significant relationship between green Human Resource Management and Environmental Performance through the mediating role of Environmental Awareness. HRM can lead to environmentally friendly behavior in the workplace that involves the implementation of environmental protection and conservation strategies. Green HRM through environmental education and training builds the desired environmental culture and informs employees about the various aspects and values of environmental management necessary to achieve environmental performance goals. The role of a comfortable work environment will be able to strengthen the employee's reasons to stay in the company. A work environment that is aligned with the green training program will have an impact on the low intention of employees to move. For this reason, companies need to align the green training program with the work environment to continue to suppress the intention of employees to move.

The results of the H3a test showed a negative and insignificant relationship, which means that the serving leadership did not moderate the influence of green human resource management on pro-environmental performance related to tasks. This is contrary to research by Ling, Linn & Wu (2016) where servant leadership influences employee behavior through social learning and social exchange mechanisms. In organizations, servant leadership and supportive attitudes towards employees make employees more determined in work related to employee duties. This behavior among employees applies to different types of performance and is not specifically related to any particular type of performance. Serving leaders encourage and direct employees toward the goals of the organization's goals. In green performance, if green performance becomes the goal of the organization, the serving leader persuades and encourages employees to perform green tasks. However, this is in line with research conducted by Mahlaga et al. (2022), where the influence of the interaction of service leadership and green resource management on a proactive environment related to tasks is not significant. This can happen due to the nature of task-related behavior as part of the employee's primary task in the organization, where, with or without a specific strategy, employees can perform their tasks, such as green activities, automatically. More importantly, the support from the leader seems to be enough for the employee to carry out his or her duties in the organization.

The results of the H3b test stated a significant negative relationship that serving leadership moderated the influence of green human resource management on pro-environmental performance. This finding is in line with Ye et al. (2019) who said that servant leadership prioritizes employee needs and emphasizes employee empowerment and ability to activate the desires and passions of employees themselves, which has been shown to motivate employees to be fully engaged and strive for great success in the workplace. Ministering leaders concentrate on employee empowerment, involving employees in decision-making and supporting employee development. This is also in accordance with Mahlaga et al. (2022) who show that servant leadership can encourage employees to show pro-environmental tendencies and develop employees' intentions to engage in environmentally friendly behavior in their job calls.

In the case of H3c stated a negative and insignificant relationship which means that serving leadership does not moderate the influence of green human resource management on environmental performance. This is contrary to Mahlaga et al. (2022) who said that servant leadership helps employees get and store the information employees need to work more effectively in the organization, servant leadership provides opportunities for employees to gain professional knowledge and also strives to provide useful information and awareness about the benefits for individuals and organizations. If the principles are based on green performance, then the serving leadership will take steps to inform employees about the principles of green performance and environmental behavior. Based on research conducted by Goranczewski (2020), one way to influence environmental awareness is the active participation of employees in the maintenance and improvement of the environmental management system itself. In this case, if employees do not actively participate even though there is a leadership that serves, it will not affect the support of green human resource management on environmental performance.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study showed that Green Human Resource Management had no effect on Task-Related Pro Environmental Performance. Green Human Resource Management has no effect on the Proactive Related Environmental Pro Performance. Green Human Resource Management has no effect on Environmental Commitment. Environmental Awareness fully mediates the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance. Environmental Awareness fully mediates the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Proactive Environmental Pro-Performance. Environmental Awareness fully mediates the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Environmental Commitment. Serving Leadership does not moderate the relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Task-Related Pro-Environmental Performance.

The study focuses on common Green Human Resource Management practices to provide insights into Pro-Environmental Performance, and obtains interesting findings. However, future studies may focus on specific green management approaches, such as employee recruitment criteria, green training, or green leadership. In addition, as different types of environmental performance have been identified in the literature, future studies may also examine other possible outcomes of Green Human Resource Management, such as green creativity and green consumer behavior. This research can be expanded by using other personal and organizational factors to explain the mediation process, such as green mindset and green empowerment. It is also suggested that

further research be conducted to test additional moderation alternatives that have the potential to strengthen the relationship between Green Human Resources and Pro-Environmental Performance, such as intrinsic rewards and supervisor personality traits. The study consisted of a single quantitative study and used cross-sectional surveys to collect data. Therefore, qualitative research or a mixed-method approach that applies time lag for data collection is highly recommended.

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